

PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE IMPACT OF INTERNET COMMUNICATION ON YOUTH'S SOCIAL BEHAVIOR. A STUDY THROUGH THE METHODOLOGY OF RICHARD S. LAZARUS "COPYING BEHAVIOR DETECTION"

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Abstract. *The formation of information and psychological security in the world community and the attitude to this process, the role of electronic media and Internet networks in the process of globalization, and their impact on the processes of moral and aesthetic education are among the current socio-psychological problems today. The phenomenon of Internet addiction in Uzbekistan has become a subject of research only in the last decade. Few studies have been conducted by Uzbek scientists in this area, and the main focus is on studying the negative impact of addiction to computer games on the psychological development of children. This article presents the results of the study of Internet-induced changes in the behavior of students who actively use the Internet.*

Keywords: *computer game addiction, Coping behavior, Self-confidence, correlation.*

The phenomenon of Internet addiction in Uzbekistan has become a subject of research only in the last decade. Few studies have been conducted by Uzbek scientists in this area, and the main focus is on studying the negative impact of addiction to computer games on the psychological development of a child. N.M. Dolimova covered the issue of "Features of psychological diagnostics and correction of adolescents addicted to computer games", in which she revealed an increase in anxiety and aggression in adolescents with addiction to computer games (2010). I.I. Rakhimova studied "Psychological features of addiction to computer games" (2018). L.A. Nigmatulina studied "The impact of addiction to computers on personality characteristics" (2019). S.B. Shukurov conducted a scientific study on "Identifying psychological factors that cause Internet addiction in students and improving ways to eliminate it" (2022). S.N. Arifkhanova conducted a scientific study on "Destructive methods of influencing the youth audience on the Internet" (2022).

The purpose of the study is to identify the socio-psychological characteristics of the personality of young students who are active users of the Internet. The subject of the study is the personality characteristics, factors and components of their dependence, manifested in the social behavior of young students who are active users of Internet communications.

Research methods: During the research, interview and observation methods were used, as well as the Richard S. Lazarus "Determination of Coping Behavior" test, the statistical reliability of the results was confirmed by the K. Pearson p-correlation coefficient from mathematical statistical methods.

Methodology: The results obtained using the Lazarus (Richard S. Lazarus) questionnaire for determining "Coping Behavior" (Behavioral Coping) allow us to identify the following specific features of the coping strategies of Internet communication users, where $p \leq 0.05$ is an indicator of a significant relationship between variables.

Results: We examine the correlation between the social behavior strategies of different Internet activity groups to identify strategies for identifying them in stressful situations in behavior (Table 1).

Table 1.
Relationships between coping strategies and the manifestation of antisocial behavior in young students

survival strategies	Manifestations of social behavior				
	Reluctance to communicate	Social desirability	Social flexibility	Demonstrative behavior	Transparency behavior
Seeking Social Support	0.769**	0.832*	0.622	0.423	0.352
Taking responsibility	0.452	0.582	-0.123	-0.835*	-0.425
Evasion of responsibility	0.498	-0.356	-0.253	0.256	0.832*
Problem Solving Plan	0.268	-0.156	-0.321**	0.365	0.153
Positive reevaluation	0.258	0.0 23	-0.812*	-0.324	0.158

Note; () - low statistical significance ($p \leq 0.05$).*

*(**) - moderate statistical significance ($p \leq 0.01$).*

Communication and social assertiveness behaviors are associated with seeking social support in problematic situations. They are correlated with the quality of social support seeking ($r=0.769^{**} \pm 0.832^{**}$; $p \leq 0.01$). Users can focus their attention on effective help such as advice, online correspondence, and empathy in their interactions with other people.

Social adaptability behaviors are negatively correlated with coping traits such as problem-solving planning ($r=-0.321^*$), positive reappraisal ($r=-0.812^{**}$) ($p \geq 0.05$). This is due to the fact that people do not quickly accept the realization of errors in decision-making, but rather realize the error after long reflection. Demonstrative behavior is negatively correlated with a sense of responsibility ($r=-0.835^{**}$; $p \geq 0.05$). This leads to a lack of responsibility in their personal relationships or a lack of confidence in their ability to be in society.

Outspoken behavior is negatively correlated with a strategy of avoiding responsibility ($r=0.832^{**}$; $p \leq 0.01$). Avoiding the responsibility of one activity due to the abundance of Internet advice and accepting it forms an instability strategy in them.

The results of the survey on the usual social behavior of users of online groups who are not active in Internet communication and those who are active in Internet communication showed a significant difference in the indicators. Adherence to new customs can be crucial for active older users in promoting a healthy lifestyle (demonstrating proper nutrition), holding sports events (including extreme sports). Active Internet users often participate in photo contests, visit prestigious and expensive places, and volunteer in various social programs, surveys, forums, and charity programs.

Conclusion. In conclusion of this study, we would like to say that we can see that regular use of the Internet, exceeding the norm, has led to the formation of new isolated qualities in human

behavior. Therefore, we need to adhere to strict standards in every activity, which will prevent serious negative effects on our psyche and health.

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